

NEUROTIC PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

Urolova D.A. Urolov Sh.S.

Relevance : Neurotic development is an intermediate clinical form between neurosis and psychopathy, and their manifestations reflect both signs of neurosis (partiality of disorders, a critical attitude towards them) and psychopathy.

With the development of neurosis, the following dynamics are observed: neurotic reactions - preneurotic states - neurosis - neurotic development of the personality. neurotic reactions

and are usually observed in people who have had signs of neuropathy since early childhood: restless sleep, poor appetite, moodiness, timidity, tearfulness, night terrors, nocturnal enuresis, stuttering, etc. Typical features are also increased fatigue, irritability and hypochondria.

The purpose of the study: To study how the neurotic development of the personality is formed.

Materials and Methods: Preneurotic states are characterized by rapidly transient affective, phobic and vegetative manifestations. There are unstable fears, exhaustion, difficulty concentrating, unwillingness to work, irritability, if necessary, to continue work, touchiness, tearfulness. There is fussiness, discomfort, if necessary, to perform small and precise movements and, if necessary, to remain still for a long time, speed and dexterity are lost.

Results and discussion: There is sweating, palpitations, increased sensitivity to temperature fluctuations, bright light and loud sounds, appetite disappears, transient pressure fluctuations are possible. Fatigue increases in the evening, does not disappear after rest, persists even after a night's sleep.

Sleep is deep and prolonged, drowsiness is observed during the day. Headaches bother me in the morning, they dissipate with the beginning of work and resume in the afternoon. Symptoms improve after 2–3 days of rest and disappear after 2–3 weeks of rest.

In the event of an unfavorable outcome of the situation, a neurosis is formed. His clinical picture is composed of two layers.

1. The first layer is neurotic symptoms. These are disorders of behavior, feelings or thinking that protect against realizing the true causes of anxiety (the primary benefit of neurosis). Symptoms can provide sympathy for the sick person (a secondary benefit of neurosis).

2. The second layer is the neurotic character. This means an inability to establish good relationships with other people, as well as one's own inner balance. A neurotic personality is characterized by anxiety manifestations, increased suggestibility, a tendency to fantasies and excessive autonomic reactions.

The neurotic character is at least a 3-storey building of the type "and you want, and it is pricked, and the mother does not order." Maybe the 4th floor: "And so that no one would guess." And the 5th: "Yes, I didn't really want to. And that's not the point at all." In such a "Khrushchev" secretly, like homeless people who have found shelter, they live: the temptations and demands of the real situation; moral prohibitions; "disguised" manifestations, reflecting forbidden, sexual and aggressive drives; protection from fear of punishment for such drives; a desperate search for support or denial of the need for it.

Conclusion: An adult may retain infantile features, corresponding to the age at which the psychotrauma was experienced. The delay in the emotional development of the personality is manifested in emotional lability, the predominance of the emotional assessment of the situation over the

intellectual, poorly controlled response. The result of the delay in formation at the thinking stage is a tendency to reasoning, abstraction, indecision and doubt. Insufficient maturity of the personality, stiffness and inertness of attitudes, inability to form a new life position interfere with an adequate assessment of the situation. Man again and again steps on the same rake.

In therapy, neurotic relationships with close people from childhood are always transferred to me. The neurotic at first believes in me, as a child believes in the omnipotence and self-sacrificing love of his parents. These infantile expectations are not justified, and then children's disappointments and resentments are revived. The symptoms are aggravated "because of a bad therapist" and I have to redeem myself. Aggression, which was redirected from my parents to myself, is directed to me.

Many demonize their parents from the very beginning: everything bad in life is because of them. Psychologists automatically become for them a parental figure and a lightning rod for a charged emotional complex. In the excitement of a dispute, the sediment that has been hidden in the patient's soul for a long time emerges, and after the discharge, there remain, as it were, de-energized ideas that are easier to revise. First of all, it is necessary to understand what blocked need the neurotic symptom satisfies, as it would be without this symptom. With the successful disclosure of unconscious material, forgotten childhood traumas are remembered and rethought in an adult way.

Together with me, the patient reveals his internal conflicts, revises the past, predicts the future, makes conscious choices, plans work on himself, finds resources in himself and relationships, begins to train missing skills, tracks positive changes, forms new tastes and values, organizes new meaningful relationships. . In the process of therapy, he reconsiders the meaning of his life and finds it not only in obtaining pleasure and avoiding

trouble, but also in building a strong family and in passing on the best in himself to children. Some go further: discover hidden talents in themselves, change boring jobs for a creative profession.